

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IFEZUE****FIRST NAME: NGOZI RUTH****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-14)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-28)
5. Video Lesson
6. Compound words (EUCLID 2019, 44)
7. Zotero reference manager

THE SKILL OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Although not a native English speaker, I have studied the English language throughout my schooling days. As the lingua franca in my country, Nigeria, the English language is introduced to students at a tender age. I was taught in the English language in all subjects and also took examinations in the same language. Daily communication in my career, such as email, verbal, presentations, and report writing, is done using English. Having been exposed to speaking, reading, listening, and writing the English language all my life, I would expect to be proficient in using the language but alas! This has not been the case. Studying topic 1 of the ACA-401D coursepack made it evident that I have mixed American and British English speaking and writing. Therefore, to be skilled in academic writing, I have to understand the difference in both types of English and choose the one that best suits my writing style. Also, to become a seasoned academic writer, I need an in-depth understanding of how to gather, review, analyze, and critique research done by other authors in the topic of interest (EUCLID 2019, 17).

The study materials for ACA-401D period one focused on the fundamentals of an academic essay. The nine-chapter coursepack discussed how students should plan, structure, and write papers. It also covered topics such as rules of styles, avoiding plagiarism,

punctuations, and the difference between American and British English. The 14-minute video explained how students could personalize and use the Response Paper (RP) template when writing RPs for the study periods.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Chapter one of the ACA-401D period one presents the objectives and basics of academic essay writing. A good essay should contain the answer to a question (thesis statement) and supporting evidence sourced from books or other credible sources (EUCLID 2019, 1). The chapter thoroughly explained the step-by-step approach students need to follow to write a good essay. Writing an essay, as described in this chapter, involves six main steps. Firstly is the need to understand and analyze the question thoroughly and develop an initial essay writing plan. Secondly, the student needs to read and do research about the topic. As stated in the text, a key feature of academic writing is that it is based on other authors' research and publications. Reading a vast number of publications and taking notes while reading, students can find evidence to develop their answers and arguments (EUCLID 2019, 2).

A third step in the essay writing process is to organize ideas generated from the research done and critically decide on points to discuss which best answers the research question. The fourth step is the essay writing using a three-step structure; the introduction, body, and conclusion. While the introduction gives an overview of the essay's main ideas, the body paragraph covers each main point, supporting points, evidence, and relevant examples. The conclusion summarizes the main focus of the essay (EUCLID 2019, 3). The fifth step is referencing. Because academic writing requires students to back up claims with evidence, the sources used must be acknowledged and referenced to avoid an academic offense; plagiarism. The final step is editing, proofreading, and submitting the essay (EUCLID 2019, 4).

While studying for my Master's degree, I was introduced to academic writing at the beginning of the program. Still, I did not have a good understanding of what it entails until the dissertation phase. I was taught these steps as listed in chapter one of the ACA-401D. Although these steps are not new to me, I have found them time-consuming and prefer to start writing straight away. This is a colossal mistake and has led to a delay in submitting my assignments within the stipulated time frame. I ran out of ideas mid-point into writing the assignment, wasting precious time. In the coming periods and courses, I have to refer back to these steps and hopefully improve my writing skills.

3) PLAGIARISM

Chapter two of the ACA-401D discussed the concept of plagiarism and how students can avoid it. The text defined plagiarism as "using a source of information without giving credit to the authors of that information"(EUCLID 2019, 5). Writers commit an offense when they use ideas and information from other authors without acknowledging

them. Students need to cite information sources using either the in-text format (RPs) or footnotes format (major papers) to avoid plagiarism. The quote's length will determine the quotation style, quotation marks for short quotes, and indentation for longer quotes.

As stated in the text, other authors' ideas should be written in my own words while retaining the original meaning (paraphrased), and these sources should be cited in the essay (EUCLID 2019, 6). Also, not all information included in an academic article requires citation. When a piece of information is common knowledge, it is not necessary to acknowledge the source. Students must reference all citations at the end of their essays, following the format dictated by the referencing style.

Although I am pretty familiar with different referencing styles, chapter two introduced me to Turabian referencing, which I am not familiar with before reading this chapter. I assumed that I have successfully paraphrased the sentence by changing some keywords in a sentence with their synonyms and rearranging the sentence structure. Having read the paraphrasing concept, it is apparent that I have been doing it the wrong way. It is now time for me to unlearn and relearn. Over the years, I was taught not to use the first-person language such as "I" in formal writing. Because of the need for students to interact with the course materials in my RP, the section on personal Vs. academic writing permits using the first-person language (EUCLID 2019, 12), which contradicts my previous knowledge on the subject.

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

The third chapter of the coursepack covers some rules of thumb for writing papers. The authors listed some advice on essential points to consider while writing papers. I have found some of this advice beneficial while planning and writing this RP. According to the text, it is very easy to get distracted while writing. Therefore, students need to have a clear focus on the topic they are interested in. It also helps to have a well-defined thesis statement from the onset and stay focused on the aspect of the subject being discussed, as it helps reduce distractions (EUCLID 2019, 14). In addition, using a variety of styles while writing makes essays interesting and creates a good impression on the reader.

While researching for assignments during my Masters' degree, I came across many ideas, some from personal experience and others from the extensive readings. These ideas were not well categorized and led to distractions from the subject of discussion. I found it challenging to group ideas and sieve out those off-topic. Hence, I wrote about all the generated ideas, which made my write-ups voluminous and lacked critical thinking. By using the Grammarly application and focusing on the topic of discussion, I hope to write critically and on the topic in the future.

5) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Although I knew there are differences regarding spelling between American and British English, it never occurred to me that some words are pronounced differently.

Studying the sixth chapter of the period one coursepack brought this to my attention. Looking back to the way I spoke and wrote the English language, I could not help but notice the mix-up of both types of English. The section on the periods, commas, and quotation marks was the most unclear. As explained in the text, American and British English though very similar, have some small but significant differences (EUCLID 2019, 27).

Spoken and written English may vary by region, with Blacks and other ethnic groups influencing the language. The native accent of these ethnic groups may influence certain words' pronunciation (EUCLID 2019, 33). For instance, the Jewish Ethnic group pronounces the word "Fat" as "shmat" and "fancy" as "schmancy." These regional variations also affect the identification of items in their locality. To illustrate, Coca-cola may be known as pop soda in one region and tunic in another region.

After studying chapter six of the period one coursepack, I found that having a grasp of the terminologies used in different fields will improve my writing skills. Also critical is the need to consult an English dictionary during the writing process (EUCLID 2019, 27).

6) VIDEO LESSON

The 14-minute video tutorial focused on how students can personalize, save and use the RP template when writing response papers. The video also covered how to write RP, choice of English, footnote vs. in-text referencing, as well as choosing headings and titles in a word document. I found the video lesson to be very informative and practical. The information gathered from this tutorial was helpful in the process of developing this RP. The section on how to use the style ribbon in MSword and punctuations in the different English types were most educative as it taught me how to navigate through the various bars in MSword quickly, a knowledge I lacked in the past.

7) COMPOUND WORDS

As defined by Dr. Abel Scribe, compound words are "two or more words that work together in a specific order. Rearranging this order will destroy the meaning of the compound word" (EUCLID 2019, 46). This section of the coursepack, though very interesting, lacked some clarity as to which compound words should be hyphenated and those that should not. According to Dr. Scribe, some compound words are written with a hyphen; for example, co-operation, full-time, while others should not be hyphenated; for instance, overrated and nonnegotiable.

8) ZOTERO REFERENCE MANAGER

While studying the period one coursepack, I was hoping to find information on how to download, install, and use the zotero reference manager in the study materials.

Unfortunately, there was no information on the subject which led to manual entry of citations and references. After successfully downloading the software and installing it, I could not use it in the RP because I lacked sufficient knowledge in transferring documents into the application. I hope the coming period will have cover this important topic as it will save a lot of precious time.

9) **CONCLUSION**

Exposure to the English language from an early stage in life is not a guarantee that an individual will be skilled at academic essay writing. Being able to write skillfully in the English language requires that the writer must, first of all, have a good understanding of the rules guiding the usage of the language. As a EUCLID student, this involves learning the basics of essay writing, writing in one English type, understanding punctuations, and familiarizing myself with the RP template.

After studying the ACA-401D period one coursepack, I believe that I am becoming proficient in using the English language, both in speaking and writing. But more work still needs to be done. As I progress in the course, I will aim to practice the rules and suggestions laid out in the period one coursepack by using them in writing response papers and in my daily communications.

REFERENCES

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